

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

A Comprehensive Review on Biological Activities of Indolo Quinoxalines and Related Scaffold

Sneha Suresh^{1*}, Ranna Vahid. A², Ganga. L³, Merin Benny ⁴, Merin.k. Varghese⁵, Sarin Santhosh⁶

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry St. Joseph's College of Pharmacy

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 08 Jun. 2026

Keywords:

Indoloquinoxaline,
Anticancer agents,
Neuroprotective activity,
Antiviral agents, DNA
intercalation, SAR studies

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20596411

ABSTRACT

Indolo-quinoxaline derivatives and its related scaffold have diverse biological activity due to their structural advantages. These compounds belong to the class of polycyclic hetro-aromatic system, mainly indolo-quinoxaline are formed by the combination of two privileged heterocyclics such as, indole and quinoxaline. This review mainly focusses on the wide therapeutic activity of such compounds and effect of structural variation up on this therapeutic activity. The following section discuss about the biological activities such as anticancer activity through DNA intercalation, stabilizing G-quadruplex etc., and also implies on overcoming multi drug resistance by varying the substitutions at different positions in those scaffolds and by introducing hybrid structures. These also look into the potential role of indolo-quinoxalines and related scaffolds as tool for neuroprotection by modulating pathways involved in neurodegenerative disorders and neural injuries, achieved by different means. With a focus on to the antiviral and antibacterial potential of structural diverse derivatives examined, the structurally imparted various mechanisms are revealed here. This manuscript also briefly discusses about some miscellaneous activities like antidiabetics, antifungal, antimalarial, antitubercular, antioxidant, antihistaminic and anti-inflammatory. And finally, a concise structural activity relationship also described on the basis of discussed compounds which explains the impact of different structural changes like planarity, substitutions etc., on biological activity. This section made a conclusion on the research gap of current studies.

INTRODUCTION

Indolo-quinoxaline derivatives and other condensed heterocycles have been

recognized as highly important in medicinal chemistry because of their diverse biological

***Corresponding Author:** Sneha Suresh

Address: Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry St. Joseph's College of Pharmacy

Email ✉: snehasuresh26072001@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

activities. The combination of electron-rich indole moieties with electron-withdrawing quinoxaline rings can mimic the natural compounds such as ellipticine and neocryptolepine. Because of their structural versatility, they can be considered as scaffolds for the design of drugs for various diseases.[1,2]

Within the field of oncology, the above-mentioned scaffolds exhibit antiproliferative activity by interacting with the DNA double helix, stabilizing G-quadruplex motifs, thereby repressing oncogene transcription, and by showing dual action against tubulin polymerization and topoisomerase 1.

In addition to their applications in oncogenic treatment, these derivatives have been observed for their neuroprotective activity in several ways. They inhibit the activity of ionotropic glutamate receptors to defend against excitotoxicity and JNK pathways during cerebral ischemia and block amyloid β fibrillation and activate the NRF2 antioxidative pathway in conditions such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases, respectively.[3,4]

The use of Indolo-quinoxalines in drug treatment is wide-ranging, including their

application as antivirals and antibiotics. Their antiviral activity arises from their capacity to stabilize the viral genome, and antibacterial activity arises from suppression of RNA synthesis controlled by genetic material. This selectivity to particular viral and bacterial actions has made them instrumental in addressing many issues currently facing.[5,6]

These heterocycles have been widely investigated to apply their potential in medicine for various biological activities, such as glucose metabolism regulation in type 2 diabetes cohorts, as well as affinity with several receptors, including AMPK and PTP1B. Besides, these heterocycles are known for their activity against fungi and malaria, including the mentioned strains that are resistant to conventional therapy. Moreover, their wide spectrum of pharmacological actions can be further complemented by the detection of antioxidant, antihistaminic, and anti-inflammatory actions. Therefore, this review was conducted to investigate the biological activities of indoloquinoxaline heterocycles.[7,8]

Indolo[2,3-b]Quinoxaline (IQ)

Ellipticine

Neocryptolepine

Fig 1: Core scaffold structures**Table 1: Properties of indolo-quinoxaline**

Properties	Value
Molecular formula	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃
Molecular weight	219.24 g/mol
Hydrogen bond donor count	1
Hydrogen bond acceptor count	2
Heavy atom count	17
Rotatable bond count	0

Fig 2: Illustration of activities of IQ**ANTI-CANCER**

Indolo-quinoxaline and related condensed heterocyclic systems represent a privileged chemical scaffold in medicinal chemistry owing to their diverse biological activities, acting primarily as strong DNA-intercalating agents and enzyme-selective inhibitors.[9]

[1] [10] [11] The combination of electron-rich indoles and electron-withdrawing quinoxalines allows these systems to be regarded as mimics of antitumor natural alkaloids such as ellipticine and neocryptolepine.[1] [2] [12]

DNA Binding and Intercalative Mechanisms

The majority of indoloquinoline analogs exert their cytotoxicity by intercalating the double helix of DNA, thereby interfering with cellular processes such as replication and transcription.[13] [14] [15] [11] Introducing fluorine substitution at position 9 and developing quaternary dicationic salt, compound 1 ($IC_{50} = 01.80 \pm 0.24 \mu M$ [MCF-7] and $4.22 \pm 0.63 \mu M$ [HeLa]) prepared by Gu et al. increases the DNA binding and

anticancer activity on MCF-7 and HeLa cell lines.[16] Moreover, according to a similarity search, the potential of some related isatin as minor groove binders is predicted.[17] Planarity is a key feature, as the non-planar 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro analog of compound 2 ($IC_{50} = 3.75 \pm 10.00 \mu M$) decreases DNA binding ability, while extending the aromatic system through benzene annulation, as seen in compound 3-10 7H-benzoindolo[2,3-b]quinolines ($Ig K_a = 6.23-6.87$), increases binding strength.[18] [19]

Compound 1

Compound 2

Compound 3

Compound 4

Compound 5

Compound 6

Compound 7

Fig 3: Compounds with DNA binding and intercalative mechanisms

Genomic Regulation and G-Quadruplex Stabilization

The use of IQ3A compounds bearing a carboxylic acid group in position 7 and a trialkylamine moiety (compound 11; $IC_{50} = 1.88 \pm 0.10 \mu M$), as described by Brito et al., is an effective means of stabilizing G-quadruplex (G4) in the promoter region of KRAS.[3] The effect results in the down-regulation of oncogenes and the induction of

apoptosis in KRAS-dependent colon carcinoma cell lines, including HCT116 cells.[3] [2] Additionally, compound 12 ($IC_{50} 2.1 \mu M$) by Li et al., indazolo-fused quinoxalines synthesized through Ugi/Ullmann cascades, has shown high antiproliferative potency against HCT116 cells.[20]

Fig 4: compounds show genomic regulation and G-quadruplex stabilization

Dual Inhibition, Cell Cycle Arrest, and AMPK Apoptosis

Some isindolo[2,1-a]quinoxaline derivatives, namely compound 13 ($IC_{50} = 0.02 \pm 0.002 \mu M$) (Diana et al.), constitute an innovative class of molecules endowed with

inhibitory activity on tubulin polymerization and topoisomerase I. Such a molecule resulted in blocking at the G₂/M phase and mitochondria depolarization in sixty human cancer cell lines.[21] Likewise, compounds 14-16 (IC₅₀ = 3.5 ± 0.3 μM, 4 ± 0.3 μM, 4 ± 0.3 μM) (Desplat et al.) isoindolo and indolo bioisosteres bearing benzyl piperidiny

fluoro-benzimidazoles proved to be effective against different leukemic cell lines.[22] Neocryptolepine analogue compounds 17-20, Altwajry et al., further reveal their antitumor potential by increasing cell aggregation in G₀/G₁, S, and G₂/M phases, leading to clear apoptotic populations.[23]

Compound 13

Compound 14

Compound 15

Compound 16

Compound 17

Compound 18

Compound 19**Compound 20****Fig 5: compound exhibits dual inhibition, cell cycle arrest, and AMPK apoptosis**

Overcoming Resistance and Chemoprevention

Through strategic substitutions, the ability for these scaffolds to overcome multi-drug resistance was achieved; for example, Compound 21 ($IC_{50} > 50 \mu\text{g/mL}$), which selectively inhibits P-glycoprotein (Pgp) and renders drug-resistant tumor cells sensitive to

conventional chemotherapy agents, such as doxorubicin.[24] Regarding to chemoprevention, Compound 22 by Skarin et al. demonstrated substantial protective activity against skin tumor promotion in mice.[25] [26].

Compound 21**Compound 22****Fig 6: compound overcoming resistance and chemoprevention**

Broad-Spectrum Activity and Hybrid Scaffolds

Screenings of various series have yielded highly potent 6-alkyl-9-substituted derivatives against human leukemia and reproductive organ cancer cell lines.[27] [13] [28] [29] Compounds 23-25 by Avula et al. demonstrated selective activity against

reproductive pathways. In this group, compounds 23 and 24 (cell viability = 72.64 ± 4.97 and 73.17 ± 2.82) exhibited a 30% cytotoxic activity against the DU-145 prostate cell line, whereas compound 25 (cell viability = 75.59 ± 3.14) appeared to be more potent against the HeLa cell line, assessed with other derivatives.[27] [28] Potentiality of the derivatives is further enhanced by

conjugating them with other drugs like artesunate or preparation of N-glycosides.[30] [29] Recently, novel derivatives such as 26, reported by Samorodova et al., 26 spectral investigations are currently underway with dyes based on the indoloquinoline structure and

palladium-catalyzed green synthesis method.[31] [32]

Fig 7: compound with broad-spectrum activity and hybrid scaffolds

NEUROPROTECTION

The indoloquinoline framework, along with its derivatives, has been shown to be a versatile tool for neuroprotection by modulating pathways involved in neurodegenerative disorders and neural injuries.[33] [34] This is achieved by means of the manipulation of glutamate receptors, the inhibition of kinases such as JNK, and the induction of antioxidants like NRF2.[4] [34]

Modulation of Ionotropic Glutamate Receptors

Neuronal death caused by excitotoxicity due to hyperstimulation of glutamate receptors on neurons is a major factor responsible for ischemia and neurodegeneration.[35] Compound 27 by Nuno A. L. Pereira et al., (30.4±2.5) (Indolo-[2,3-a] quinolizidines) has been developed as a highly potent modulator of the N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptor, providing protection against NMDAR-induced neuronal death.[36] Additionally, via in silico screening studies, compound 28 (DSX Binding Score = -107.35), Balasundaram et al., has been recognized as an allosteric

inhibitor of the iGluA2 (AMPA) receptor, which could serve well.[35]

Fig 8: compounds exhibit modulation of ionotropic glutamate receptors

Inhibition of c-Jun N-terminal Kinases (JNK) in Cerebral Ischemia

Neuronal damage caused by reperfusion-mediated oxidative stress is significantly influenced by the JNK signalling pathway. The lithium salt of 11H-indeno[1,2-b]quinoxaline-11-one oxime, or IQ-1L (compound 29- $K_d = 0.14 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{M}$ [JNK],

5.80 ± 0.70 [NRF2]), is a powerful JNK inhibitor. IQ-1L reduced the infarct area by 52% in relative to vehicle control and significantly improved neurological score assessments in rat models of focal cerebral ischemia.[34]

Compound 29

Fig 9: compound Inhibit JNK in Cerebral Ischemia

Multifunctional Anti-Alzheimer Activity

MTDLs for Alzheimer's disease are being investigated as derivatives of indoloquinoxalines. Compound 30 (AChE- 5.80 ± 0.70 , BuChE- 0.96 ± 0.31) Kanhed et al.,

have the ability to function as both amyloid beta ($A\beta_{1-42}$) fibrillation blockers and cholinesterase inhibitors (BuChE specifically). It is believed that the indoloquinoxaline framework's flat, planar

arrangement prevents pi-pi stacking in amyloid fibrils. [33]

Compound 30

Fig 10: compound with multifunctional anti-alzheimer activity

Regulation of the NRF2 Pathway in Parkinson's Disease

Indole-derivative-related scaffolds, such as compound 31 (NC001-8), have been shown to provide neuroprotection against dopaminergic neuronal loss in Parkinson's disease. By increasing the NRF2

antioxidative pathway, which lowers ROS levels and prevents apoptosis, NC001-8 enhances neuronal survival. To activate downstream antioxidant genes such as NQO1, this regulation entails the translocation of NRF2 into the nucleus.[4]

Compound 31

Fig11: compound regulate NRF2 pathway in Parkinson's disease

ANTI-VIRAL ACTIVITY

As aza-analogues of the cytotoxic alkaloids cryptolepine and ellipticine, indolo[2,3-b]quinoxalines' pharmacological profiles

have shifted toward highly specific antiviral drugs by structural optimization.[9] [14] DNA intercalation, which is defined by the planar aromatic core inserting between nucleic acid nucleobases, is the main mode of

action for these heterocycles.[37] [11] This interaction stabilizes DNA triple helices and interferes with critical steps of viral replication, particularly the uncoating of the viral genome.[25] [37] Moreover, aminoethyl substituted derivatives are potent endogenous interferon (IFN) inducers, thus boosting the host's innate immunological defense against DNA and RNA viruses.[5] [6]

Disruption of Viral Uncoating via DNA Intercalation

Compound 32 (B-220) (Wilhelmsson et al., 2008) is used as a traditional DNA intercalator, exhibiting remarkable antiviral

activity against the herpes viruses, namely human cytomegalovirus (HCMV), HSV-1, and VZV.[1] [25] [37] [11] From spectroscopic studies, it is found that these compounds display a specific affinity for AT-region genome sequences, which are important in targeting the viral genome at the time of de-capsulation.[37] Moreover, the thermal stability of these frameworks, often used in optoelectronic dyes, increases their rigidity during intercalation and enhances their effectiveness in stabilizing the viral genome during the decapsulation pathway.[31] [32]

Compound 32

Fig 12: compound disrupt of viral uncoating via DNA intercalation

Induction of Endogenous Interferon (IFN)

The specific aminoethyl analogs, including Compound 33 for VSV, exhibit strong interferon (IFN)-inducing activity.[5] [38] [6] Such analogues show higher antiviral activity when used in a prophylactic mode (24 hours prior to infection) rather than a therapeutic one, which is a hallmark of a

cytokine-based mechanism of protection.[38] [18] The studies conducted on Compound 33 reveal its high efficiency in inducing a long-lasting IFN response without a significant increase in inflammatory markers (MCP-1, complement).[6]

Compound 33

Fig 13: compound show induction of endogenous interferon

SAR: Influence of Molecular Planarity and Annulation

SAR investigations have demonstrated that molecular planarity is mandatory for achieving high DNA-binding efficiency and antiviral efficacy.[19] For instance, non-planar derivatives like tetrahydro-indolo quinoxaline (Compound 34) exhibit less intercalation potential than their fully aromatic counterparts. On the other hand,

while adding an additional benzene ring to maximize the compound's protection (Compound 35) improves its DNA-binding ability, this modification may lead to decreased direct antiviral and IFN-inducing properties, suggesting that the tetracyclic structure is more suitable for antiviral applications.[19] [18]

Compound 34

Compound 35

Fig 14: compounds have influence in antiviral activity based on its SAR

High-Potency Dimeric and Novel Heterocyclic Scaffolds

The current advancements in organic synthesis strategies, especially the implementation of green chemistry

approaches employing the catalyst, have made it possible to create highly efficient dimeric indoloquinoxaline derivatives (Compound 36).[9] [10] [37] The dissociation constants of these dimeric systems are much higher than those of the

corresponding monomers and have greater efficacy than that of conventional antiviral compounds such as ganciclovir.[37] Additionally, the creation of novel pentacyclic heterocyclic systems (Compound 37), which are claimed to provide a high yield of 71.6% (Bobokhidze, 2024) through

palladium-assisted C–C and C–N couplings, has led to new perspectives on designing next-generation intercalating antiviral drugs.[1] [31]

Fig 15: high-potency dimeric and novel heterocyclic scaffolds

ANTI-BACTERIAL

Indolo[2,3-b]quinoxalines (IQ) and their analogs are an extremely significant group of nitrogenous heterocyclic molecules, which have been extensively utilized in medicinal chemistry to act as antibacterial agents.[32] [9] Quinoxaline derivatives have been found to show considerable medicinal significance, including antibacterial action.^{2 37} The biological significance of indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline derivatives is well recognized, especially their antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. [31] [40] [41] [42]

Prevention of DNA-Directed RNA Synthesis

The antibacterial efficacy of all the selected compounds was examined in vitro against *MRSA*, *E. coli*, and *K. pneumoniae*, utilizing the agar cup diffusion technique for the screening of susceptibility testing and twofold serial dilution for the determination of MIC. Quinoxalines exhibit strong antimicrobial properties due to their ability to inhibit DNA-dependent RNA synthesis by interfering with the binding to CpG sites on DNA.[40] Compound 38, Abdu-Allah et al. revealed the highest activity against the three strains, even exceeding the reference drug (gentamycin) with a MIC value of $25.00 \pm 00 \mu\text{M/mL}$ against *E. coli*. [40] The results of screening revealed that the substituted quinoxaline compounds having electron-withdrawing groups mediated moderate to significant antibacterial activity as compared

to the standard drug ciprofloxacin.[41] Gupta et al. (2013) reported Compound 39 was found to exhibit the most potent in vitro antimicrobial activity with the MIC value of

$14.00 \pm 00 \mu\text{g/ml}$ against *Staphylococcus pyogenes*.[41]

Fig 16: compound Inhibit JNK in Cerebral Ischemia

Inhibition of Mycobacterium Adenosine Kinase (Rv2202c)

In the first study, these polycyclic compounds were tested for their antimycobacterial activity, including against extensively drug-resistant strains, and facilitated a moderate bacteriostatic effect against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv.[7] Molecular docking data suggest

that 4-alkyl-4H-thieno[2',3':4,5]pyrrolo[2,3-b]quinoxalines are likely inhibitors of adenosine kinase (Rv2202c).[7] Compound 40 Sadykhov et al. demonstrated a MIC value of $12.50 \pm 0.00 \mu\text{g/mL}$ against both the H37Rv strain and an extensively drug-resistant (XDR) strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* with an IC₅₀ value of $11.80 \pm 1.40 \mu\text{g/mL}$ against Vero cells.[7]

Compound 40

Fig 17: compound Inhibit Mycobacterium Adenosine Kinase

In Vitro Growth Inhibition of Pathogenic Strains

All the synthesized compounds were also screened in vitro for antibacterial assay

against Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) and Gram-positive (*Salmonella typhi* and *Bacillus subtilis*) pathogenic bacteria in comparison to the standard streptomycin.[39] It was observed

that the compounds bearing both electron-donating and -withdrawing groups exhibited varying degrees of potent activity against bacterial and fungal strains.[39] Compound 41 has an excellent Inhibition Zone (IZ) value

of 21.00 ± 0.00 mm against *S. aureus*, as shown by Durgarao et al.[39]

Compound 41

Fig 18: compound perform in vitro growth inhibition of pathogenic strains

MISCELLANEOUS ACTIVITY

Anti-Diabetic Activity: In medicinal chemistry, indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline derivatives are considered crucial for several medicinal applications, including antidiabetic activity.[7] Compound 42 (Kunjiappan et al., efficiency of glucose utilization $58.56 \pm 04.54\%$ at 40 mg) was encapsulated into keratin nanoparticles for regulating glucose metabolism in 3T3-L1 adipocytes.[8] The molecules possess

significant interactions within the binding sites of AMPK and PTP1B, two crucial therapeutic targets for treating type 2 diabetes based on molecular docking analysis.[8] Molecular docking studies and computational techniques were employed for evaluating other similar frameworks, such as substituted benzimidazoles, for potential anti-diabetes properties.[10]

Compound 42

Fig 19: anti-diabetic compound

Anti-Fungal Activity: Fungus-borne disease infections have become quite common, which necessitated the development of newer

indoloquinoxaline antimycotics.[41] Compound 39 (Gupta et al., MIC values of 28 and 19 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ against *Candida albicans* and

Aspergillus niger, respectively) was the most effective antifungal compound in its class.[41]

Compound 39

Fig 20: compound exhibit anti-fungal activity

Anti-Malarial Activity: The quinoxaline and indolo-quinoline derivatives are famous for their activity against malaria.[10] Another compound, 43 (Wang et al., 02.10 ± 00.00 nM vs. NF54), was developed as an effective

antimalarial agent. [29] Such hybrids affect erythrocytic forms of parasites, including those resistant to chloroquine.[29]

Compound 43

Fig 21: compound exert anti-malarial activity

Anti-Tubercular Activity: The antimycobacterial activity of new polycyclic derivatives, including 4-alkyl-4H-thieno[2',3':4,5]pyrrolo[2,3-b]quinoxalines, against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv was tested.[7] Compound 40 (Sadykhov et

al., MIC 12.50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) correlated with antitubercular activity against susceptible and extensively drug-resistant (XDR) strains.[7] Quinoxalines are also known to have strong anti-mycobacterial properties in general drug discovery settings. [43]

Compound 40

Fig 22: compound shows anti-tubercular activity

Antioxidant and Antihistaminic Activity: Phenylpyrazolo indoloquinoline derivatives: A study of their multifunctional pharmacological profile. [44] Compound 44 (Sridevi et al., 59.40%) demonstrated

superior free radical scavenging activity in DPPH tests.[44] Compound 45 (Sridevi et al., protection 90.9%) demonstrated strong antihistamine effects in guinea pig tests using the histamine chamber method.[44]

Compound 44

Compound 45

Fig 23: compounds with antioxidant and antihistaminic activity

Anti-Inflammatory Activity: Novel hexahydro indoloquinoxaline compounds were produced and tested for in vivo anti-inflammatory efficacy using carrageenan-induced rat paw edema techniques.[40]

Compound 46 (Abdu-Allah et al., edema inhibition 79.00% at 5 hours) was the most active drug in the series. [40]

Compound 46

Fig 24: anti-inflammatory compound

Structural Activity Relationship of Indolo-Quinoxaline

Table 2: SAR Table for Indolo-quinoxaline Derivatives

Structural Feature / Modification	Biological Effect / Activity Relationship	Example Compound(s)
Molecular Planarity	Mandatory for efficient DNA intercalation and binding. Non-planar analogs exhibit significantly decreased binding ability.	Compound 2, 30, 34
Benzene Annulation	Extending the aromatic system increases DNA-binding strength, though it may decrease direct antiviral or interferon-inducing properties.	Compounds 3, 10, 35
Position 9 Substitution (Fluorine) & Quaternary Dicationic Salts	Increases DNA binding affinity and anticancer activity specifically against MCF-7 and HeLa cell lines.	Compound 1
Aminoethyl Substitutions	Act as potent endogenous interferon (IFN) inducers, enhancing the host's innate immunological defense against viruses.	Compound 33
Strategic Substitutions for Resistance	Allows the scaffold to selectively inhibit P-glycoprotein (Pgp), rendering drug-resistant tumor cells sensitive to chemotherapy.	Compound 21
Dimerization (Dimeric Systems)	Results in significantly higher dissociation constants and greater antiviral efficacy compared to corresponding monomers.	Compound 36
Electron-Withdrawing Groups on Quinoxaline	Correlates with moderate-to-significant antibacterial activity against strains like <i>E. coli</i> and MRSA.	Compound 38

4-Alkyl-4H-thieno Fusion	Shifts activity toward Mycobacterium Adenosine Kinase inhibition, providing potent antitubercular effects against XDR strains.	Compound 40
--------------------------	--	-------------

Fig 25: SAR illustration of indolo-quinoxaline

CONCLUSION

This review highlights the diverse biological activities of indolo-quinoxaline and related chemical frameworks, particularly their anticancer, neuroprotective, antiviral, antibacterial, and other effects, such as antidiabetic, antifungal, antimalarial, antitubercular, antioxidant, antihistaminic, and anti-inflammatory activities. These findings suggest that quinoxaline architectures interact with various biological targets. A comparison of structure and activity reveals that structural changes, such as annulation, fluorination, carboxylic acid substitution, and addition of electron-withdrawing groups, significantly modulate

biological activity and therapeutic potential. The review also summarizes evidence supporting the biological potential of indolo-quinoxaline derivatives, established through experimental and computational methods, including MTT cytotoxicity assays, molecular docking, DNA binding, enzyme inhibition, antimicrobial and antiviral screenings etc. However, none of the existing studies examine toxicity, indicating a need for further research in this area. Additionally, many derivatives remain unexplored, suggesting more opportunities for future application. The study areas can also be improved by incorporating several in-vivo and in-vitro analysing methods. Indolo-quinoxaline-based compounds hold great

potential for successful drug development and future therapeutic applications via proper structural optimization and pharmacological evaluation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Sincerely express our heartfelt gratitude to God Almighty for his blessing and guidance throughout the completion of this review work.

We express our special and heartfelt gratitude to Mrs. Ranna Vahid. A, Department of

pharmaceutical chemistry, St. Joseph's College of Pharmacy, for her exceptional guidance, constant encouragement, valuable suggestions and support during the preparation of this manuscript

We also extend the respectful thanks to Dr. Sr. Daisy P.A, Principal St. Joseph's College of Pharmacy and Dr. Vinod .B, HOD, Department of pharmaceutical chemistry, St. Joseph's College of Pharmacy.

REFERENCES

1. Bobokhidze L. Novel Synthetic Investigation in the Field of INDOLO[2,3-B]QUINOXALINE Ring Containing Tetracyclic and Pentacyclic Heterocycles. New Materials Compounds and Applications. 2024 Apr 15. doi:10.62476/NMCA8113
2. Hirata K, Araya J, Nakaike S, Kitamura K, Ishida T. Side Chain-Dependent Binding of Antitumor Indoloquinoxaline Derivatives to DNA: Comparative Spectroscopic and Viscometric Measurements. Chem Pharm Bull. 2001;49(1):44–8. doi:10.1248/cpb.49.44
3. Brito H, Martins AC, Lavrado J, Mendes E, Francisco AP, Santos SA, et al. Targeting KRAS Oncogene in Colon Cancer Cells with 7-Carboxylate Indolo[3,2-b]quinoline Tri-Alkylamine Derivatives. Amin ARMR, editor. PLoS ONE. 2015 May 29;10(5):e0126891. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0126891
4. Wei PC, Lee-Chen GJ, Chen CM, Ru Wu Y. Neuroprotection of Indole - Derivative Compound NC001 - 8 by the Regulation of the NRF2 Pathway in Parkinson' s Disease Cell Models - Wei - 2019 - Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity - Wiley Online Library <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1155/2019/5074367>
5. Antonovych GV, Zholobak NM, Lyakhov SA, Shibinska MO, Andronati SA, Spivak MY. Dose-dependent IFN-stimulating and immunomodulating properties of 6H-indolo[2,3-B] quinoxaline derivatives. Mikrobiol Z. 2012;74(4):79–86.
6. Antonovych GV, Zholobak NM, Shibinska MO, Spivak MYa. The effect of antiviral substance 6-(2-morpholin-4-yl-ethyl)-6H-indolo [2,3-b]quinoxaline upon biomarkers of inflammation. Biopolym Cell. 2015 Aug 20;31(4):264–71. doi:10.7124/bc.0008EA
7. Sadykhov GA, Belyaev DV, Khramtsova EE, Vakhrusheva DV, Krasnoborova SY, Dianov DV, et al. 4-Alkyl-4H-thieno[2',3':4,5]pyrrolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline Derivatives as New Heterocyclic Analogues of Indolo[2,3-b]quinoxalines: Synthesis and Antitubercular Activity. International Journal of Molecular Sciences. 2025 Jan;26(1):369. doi:10.3390/ijms26010369
8. Kunjiappan S, Theivendren P, Pavadai P, Govindaraj S, Sankaranarayanan M,

- Somasundaram B, et al. Design and in silico modeling of Indoloquinoxaline incorporated keratin nanoparticles for modulation of glucose metabolism in 3T3 - L1 adipocytes. *Biotechnology Progress*. 2018;36(1):e2904. doi:10.1002/btpr.2904
9. Alsubari A, Al Mamari K, kandri rodi Y, Essassi EM. SYNTHESIS AND SPECTROSCOPIC CHARACTERIZATION OF BIS- INDOLO[2,3-b]QUINOXALINE DERIVATIVES. Vol. 22. 2024 Mar 13;22:57–64.
 10. Shaikh SM, Ansari GM, Karbari ZZ, Babre AA, Borge VV, Bangade VM, et al. [EMIM]AlCl₄-ionic liquid catalyzed mechanochemically assisted green approach towards the synthesis of quinoxaline, 6H-indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline and benzimidazole derivatives. *Results in Chemistry*. 2024 Dec 1;12:101884. doi:10.1016/j.rechem.2024.101884
 11. Zhang* H. A green synthesis of indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline derivatives. *JOURNAL OF CHEMICAL RESEARCH*; 2014 [cited 2026 Jan 6]. A green synthesis of indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline derivatives. <https://doi.org/10.3184/174751914X14146737095013>
 12. Synthesis, anticancer and cytostatic activity of some 6H-indolo[2,3-b]quinoxalines. *Acta pharmaceutica*. Available from: DOI:10.2478/v10007-009-0040-9
 13. Hari Narayana Moorthy NS, Karthikeyan C, Trivedi P. Design, synthesis, cytotoxic evaluation, and QSAR study of some 6H-indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline derivatives. *Journal of Enzyme Inhibition and Medicinal Chemistry*. 2010 Jun 1;25(3):394–405. doi:10.3109/14756360903190747 PubMed PMID: 20233012.
 14. Helissey P, Desbène-Finck S, Giorgi-Renault S. Alkylation of 5- and 6-Methylindolo[2,3-b]quinoxalines: Revised Structures of the N,N'-Dimethylated Salts. *European Journal of Organic Chemistry*. 2005;2005(2):410 – 5. doi:10.1002/ejoc.200400386
 15. Malah TE, El-Rashedy AA, Hegab MI, Awad HM, Shamroukh AH. Click synthesis of novel 6-((1H-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)methyl)-6H-indolo[2,3-b]quinoxalines for in vitro anticancer evaluation and docking studies. *New J Chem*. 2024 Jun 17;48(24):11064–78. doi:10.1039/D3NJ05761E
 16. Zhenyu G, Li Y, Ma S, Li S, Zhou G, Ding S, et al. Synthesis, cytotoxic evaluation and DNA binding study of 9-fluoro-6H-indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline derivatives. *RSC Adv*. 2017;7(66):41869–79. doi:10.1039/C7RA08138C
 17. Maldonado M, Santiago Á, Pastor N, Alvarez L, Razo R. Isatin derivatives as DNA minor groove-binding agents: a structural and theoretical study. *Structural Chemistry*. 2020 Aug 1;31. doi:10.1007/s11224-020-01497-w
 18. Shibinskaya MO, Karpenko AS, Lyakhov SA, Andronati SA, Zholobak NM, Spivak NY, et al. Synthesis and biological activity of 7H-benzo[4,5]indolo[2,3-b]-quinoxaline derivatives. *Eur J Med Chem*. 2011 Feb;46(2):794–8. doi:10.1016/j.ejmech.2010.11.040.
 19. Shibinskaya M, Karpenko A, Lyakhov S, Andronati S, Zholobak N, Spivak N, et al. Synthesis and Biological Activity of 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydroindolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline Derivatives. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Pharmacology*. 2015 Jun 1;2:140–7. doi:10.1166/jpsp.2015.1048
 20. Li Y, He L, Qin H, Liu Y, Yang B, Xu Z, et al. A Facile Ugi/Ullmann Cascade Reaction to Access Fused Indazolo-Quinoxaline Derivatives with Potent Anticancer Activity. *Molecules*. 2024 Jan 1;29. doi:10.3390/molecules29020464

21. Patrizia D, Annamaria M, Barraja P, Montalbano AM, Dattolo G, Cirrincione G, et al. Isoindolo[2,1-a]quinoxaline Derivatives, Novel Potent Antitumor Agents with Dual Inhibition of Tubulin Polymerization and Topoisomerase I | Journal of Medicinal Chemistry. Available from: <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/jm070834t>
22. Desplat V, Moreau S, Belisle-Fabre S, Thiolat D, Juliette. Synthesis and evaluation of the antiproliferative activity of novel isoindolo[2,1-a]quinoxaline and indolo[1,2-a]quinoxaline derivatives. Journal of Enzyme Inhibition and Medicinal Chemistry. 2011 Sep 14;26(5):657–67. doi:10.3109/14756366.2010.548326
23. Altwajry N, El-Ghlban S, E. I, El-Bahnsawye M, I. Bayomi A, M. Samaka R, et al. In Vitro and In Vivo Antitumor Activity of Indolo[2,3-b] Quinolines, Natural Product Analogs from Neocryptolepine Alkaloid. Molecules. 2021 Feb 1;26(3):754. doi:10.3390/MOLECULES26030754
24. Smith CD, Myers CB, Zilfou JT, Smith SN, Lawrence DS. Indoloquinoxaline compounds that selectively antagonize P-glycoprotein. Oncology Research, Vol. 12, pp. 219–229, 2000. doi:10.3727/096504001108747710.
25. Engqvist R, Stensland B, Bergman J. Reduction of indolo[2,3-b]quinoxalines. Tetrahedron. 2005 May 2;61(18):4495–500. doi:10.1016/j.tet.2005.02.060
26. 2Skarin T, Lundh Rozell B, Bergman J, Toftgård R, Möller L. Protection against 12-O-tetradecanoylphorbol-13-acetate induced skin-hyperplasia and tumor promotion, in a two-stage carcinogenesis mouse model, by the 2,3-dimethyl-6(2-dimethylaminoethyl)-6H-indolo-[2,3-b]quinoxaline analogue of ellipticine. Chemico-Biological Interactions. 1999 Sep 30;122(2):89–106. doi:10.1016/S0009-2797(99)00117-9
27. Avula S, Komsani J, Koppireddi S, Yadla R, Kanugula A, Kotamraju S. Synthesis and cytotoxicity of novel 6H-indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline derivatives. Medicinal Chemistry Research. 2012 Aug 1;22. doi:10.1007/s00044-012-0373-7
28. Sai D, M Babu2 N, V M. Synthesis, Characterization of some Novel 6h-Indolo (2, 3-b) Quinoxaline Fused Azetidinones as Potential Bioactive Molecules. 2012. Available from: <https://www.indianjournals.com/article/ajrc-8-12-002>
29. Wang N, Wicht KJ, Shaban E, Ngoc TA, Wang MQ, Hayashi I, et al. Synthesis and evaluation of artesunate–indoloquinoline hybrids as antimalarial drug candidates. Med Chem Commun. 2014 Jun 24;5(7):927–31. doi:10.1039/C4MD00091A
30. Driller KM, Libnow S, Hein M, Harms M, Wende K, Lalk M, et al. Synthesis of 6H-indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline-N-glycosides and their cytotoxic activity against human ceratinocytes (HaCaT). Org Biomol Chem. 2008;6(22):4218. doi:10.1039/b812308j
31. Hung TQ, Hoang DH, Thang NN, Dang TT, Ayub K, Villinger A, et al. Palladium catalyzed synthesis and physical properties of indolo[2,3-b]quinoxalines. Org Biomol Chem. 2014 Jul 23;12(32):6151–66. doi:10.1039/C4OB00841C
32. K SHARMA B, M SHAIKH A, CHACKO S, M KAMBLE R. Synthesis, Spectral, Electrochemical and Theoretical Investigation of indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline dyes derived from Anthraquinone for n–type materials. Journal of Chemical Sciences. [cited 2026 Mar 8]. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12039-017-1252-z>
33. Kanhed AM, Patel DV, Patel NR, Sinha A, Thakor PS, Patel KB, et al. Indoloquinoxaline

- derivatives as promising multi-functional anti-Alzheimer agents. *Journal of Biomolecular Structure and Dynamics*. 2020;40(6):2498–515. doi:10.1080/07391102.2020.1840441 PubMed PMID: 33111617.
34. Schepetkin IA, Chernysheva GA, Aliev OI, Kirpotina LN, Smol'yakova VI, Osipenko AN, et al. Neuroprotective Effects of the Lithium Salt of a Novel JNK Inhibitor in an Animal Model of Cerebral Ischemia–Reperfusion. *Biomedicines*. 2022 Aug 29;10(9). doi:10.3390/biomedicines10092119
 35. Padmanabhan B. Identification of novel modulators for ionotropic glutamate receptor, iGluA2 by in-silico screening | Theoretical Biology and Medical Modelling | Springer Nature Link [Internet]. 2013 [cited 2026 Mar 14]. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/1742-4682-10-46>
 36. Pereira NAL, Sureda FX, Pérez M, Amat M, Santos MMM. Enantiopure Indolo[2,3-a]quinolizidines: Synthesis and Evaluation as NMDA Receptor Antagonists. *Molecules*. 201 Aug;21(8):1027. doi:10.3390/molecules21081027
 37. Wilhelmsson LM, Kingi N, Bergman J. Interactions of antiviral indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline derivatives with DNA. *J Med Chem*. 2008 Dec 25;51(24):7744–50. doi:10.1021/jm800787b PubMed PMID: 19053744.
 38. Shibinskaya M, Lyakhov S, Mazepa A, Andronati S, Turov A, Zholobak N, et al. Synthesis, cytotoxicity, antiviral activity and interferon inducing ability of 6-(2-aminoethyl)-6H-indolo[2,3-b]quinoxalines. *European journal of medicinal chemistry*. 2010 Mar 1;45:1237–43. doi:10.1016/j.ejmech.2009.12.014
 39. Durgarao BV, Sirisha DVL, Apparao K, Narasingrao V, Balageeta K, Rao NK. An Efficient One Pot Synthesis and Biological Activities of 6H-Indolo[2,3-b]quinoxalines Promoted by Palladium Acetate as Catalyst. *ajc*. 2024 Aug 30;36(9):2001–5. doi:10.14233/ajchem.2024.31782
 40. Hajjaj H. M. Abdu-Allah, Samia G. Abdel-Moty, Helal F. Heta. *Der Pharma Chemica*; 2016 [cited 2026 Mar 14]. p. 192–201. Synthesis of hexahydro-6H-indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline derivatives as potential antibacterial and anti-inflammatory agents.
 41. Anil Kumar Gupta.. 2016 [cited 2026 Mar 14]. Synthesis, characterization and biological evaluation of novel substituted-1-(4-substituted benzyl)-1h-indolo (2, 3-b) quinoxaline n-benzyl indole-2,3-dione moieties.
 42. Sadykhov G, Verbitskiy E. Modern methods for the synthesis of indolo[2,3-b]quinoxalines (microreview). *Chemistry of Heterocyclic Compounds*. 2022;58. doi:10.1007/s10593-023-03144-8
 43. Shaikh SM, Ansari GM, Karbari ZZ, Babre AA, Borge VV, Bangade VM, et al. [EMIM]AlCl₄-ionic liquid catalyzed mechanochemically assisted green approach towards the synthesis of quinoxaline, 6H-indolo[2,3-b]quinoxaline and benzimidazole derivatives. *Results in Chemistry*. 2024 Dec 1;12:101884. doi:10.1016/j.rechem.2024.101884
 44. CH.SRIDEVI, K.BALAJI, A.NAIDU. Synthesis and Pharmacological Evaluation of Some Phenylpyrazolo Indoquinoxaline Derivatives - Sridevi - 2011 - *Journal of Chemistry - Wiley Online Library*. 2011 [cited 2026 Mar 14]. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1155/2011/584817>.

HOW TO CITE: Sneha Suresh*, Ranna Vahid. A, Ganga. L, Merin Benny, Merin.k. Varghese, Sarin Santhosh, A Comprehensive Review on Biological Activities of Indolo Quinoxalines and Related Scaffold, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2026, Vol 4, Issue 6, 2097-2120. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20596411>

